

Entrepreneurial features of producership

Normatova Gavhar Mahmud qizi

Uzbek State

Institute of Arts and Culture, "Producer", 3rd year
student

Annotation: A producer is a person who is in charge of the ideological, artistic, organizational and financial control of a film company, or who organizes the administrative and financial work of a concert or show program prepared by a singer or variety group. This article discusses the entrepreneurial features of producership.

Keywords: producer, entrepreneur; artistic thinking; stage.

As a result of the rapid development of science (artistic thinking and data collection) and the emergence of new technologies, modern art has reached its highest creative stage. Nowadays, any stage play is a perfect system with its own «language", "code", and "symbol". To understand its language, its sign, certain intellectual knowledge is required. The real spectator must understand the alphabet of artistic creation, the artistic image, the language of the theater. modern art demands that artists should be as diligent as possible in creating and virtualizing each scene in their imagination in order to capture the audience's attention.

The producer profession began to take shape in 1910 in Hollywood. Initially, the producer responded to a creative, financial, organizational issue during the filming process. In this way, producers have a special place in American cinema. Renowned producer Irvin Talberg has a special place in American cinema. Following Talberg's death in return for his work in cinema, the USA film Academy established The Irvin Talberg Award. This award is given annually to the best producer. From year to year, the demand for producers has increased and this profession has spread to Western Europe. In particular, the demand for producers in pop shows, television and theatres has increased. In the 19th century, the audience visited the theater for an actor, in the 20th century, they came to see the work of the director and in the 21st century,

they will rush to see the work of producer. It would be correct to call the rapidly evolving 21st century " the producer theater age". It is this profession who chooses the work, invites the director and actors, and pledges his money. The success or failure of a play also depends on the producer. Even today, the USA film company Hollywood is the world's largest film producer thanks to the work of producer. In this film industry well-known producers like David Sleznik , Jeyms Kameron, B. Brukhaymer, Stiven Spilberg, Robert Zemiks, Devid Haymak, Kristin Vashon, Emmanuel Lyubeski, Lourens Vender succeed in creating film masterpieces. The collaboration between the producer and the director has developed, and examples of co-creation towards ideas and goals have emerged. This led to the development of the production profession in all fields of art.

A producer is the author of a new work of art being created, and in the next process can be a manager, an organizer, sometimes a director, an impresario, or even a lead actor. In implementing the project idea, the producer selects a profitable actor, forms a team, selects a repertoire, organizes an advertising campaign and launches a mechanism. At the same time, the producer is responsible for the project idea. The film industry is developing precisely due to the activities of producers. It is these people who make money for the expenses incurred in front of sponsors and investors. The film producer comes up with the project , finds a good script and directors. Every producer has their own ultimate goal. He analyzes today's market and makes a plan for tomorrow. This is a direct risk. What is the responsibility of a film producer ? First of all, the film producer must be able to calculate what the audience wants to see on the screen, what kind of film and how many viewers want to see the film. The producer then chooses a director and screenwriter who can make a film of a certain genre. Directs the playwright's work in the script creating process. Once the script is completed, the producer will deal with the financial support. He appeals to state and non-state enterprises on this issue. Participating in the financing of a good film means the beginning of a filming campaign. In addition, the producer is actively involved in the selection of actors, film crew, artist and composer. But its main function is advertising

and film distribution. Once the film is ready, the process of popularizing it begins. This process is carried out by the producer in three directions: it is offered to the heads of cinemas, TV companies and DVD makers. In one of his speeches on the development of the national cinematography and film industry, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "If we want to glorify our great nation and glorify the name of Uzbekistan to the whole world, we must do it first of all with the help of cinematography. It is through the art of cinema that we can conquer the screens of the world, in this way gaining the attention of the people of the world. To do this, we must once again use our strength and capabilities, our creative potential". The success of the film is not a one-man show, of course. Both victory and defeat will belong to the whole creative team. Cinema is an art form created as a team. Solidarity is an important feature. The producer is responsible for creating all the conditions for the creative team. When we talk about the producer, we only see a person who cares about the income that comes from the film. The essence of production seems to be to invest in something and make a profit from it. But this process is not built solely on personal interests. Well-known foreign producers are not just entrepreneurs or high-income people. They are people who have an in-depth understanding of the film, who can analyze the success of the film, how to act in order to gain the audience's attention. In addition, the number of giant film companies is growing and this process is creating a strong competitive environment. Producers strive to bring the director's creative product to the forefront in this competitive environment. They are constantly working on themselves.

From its very beginning the job of producer has covered both financial and creative responsibilities without finding itself —from a conceptual point of view— confined primarily to one side or the other. Only the evolution of the industry itself, along with the aptitudes of those who have held this job, has tipped the balance toward technical knowledge or, less frequently, toward its creative capacity. The role of the film producer has certainly passed through very diverse stages of development in its first century of existence. Moments of splendour and grand protagonism —the Hollywood studio system era— have been succeeded by others of downsizing and marginalization —with

the peak of so-called auteur cinema in the sixties. The last three decades, however, have witnessed an increased appreciation of the figure of the producer and, more precisely, the creative producer. Some authors underline its exceptionalism, as if it were a *rara avis*; others, on the contrary, maintain that producing and creativity have always been synonymous terms. The producer today, in order to be able to produce properly, must be able not merely to criticize, but be able to answer the old question what or why. He must be able, if necessary, to sit down and write the scene, and if he is criticizing a director, he must be able not merely to say 'I don't like it', but tell him how he would direct it himself. He must be able to go into the cutting room, and if he doesn't like the cutting of the sequence, which is more often true than not, he must be able to recut the sequence. The film industry tends to divide film producers into two rather vaguely defined camps: the creative producer and the financial producer. Few people are uniquely talented in both fields. Theoretically, an effective producing combination is one where two people —one creatively skilled and one financially inclined— work together on developing and producing projects

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